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on behalf of the **SoLAr Collaboration**

The SoLAr project

A dual-readout pixelated anode for multipurpose LArTPCs

The DUNE Phase II and the Module of Opportunity

➤ DUNE Phase I

(2×10 kton detectors - 1.2 MW beam)

- ✓ mass ordering
- ⚙️ more exposure needed for full physics program

➤ DUNE Phase II

- Upgrade to 2.4 MW beam power
- Enhanced Near Detector complex
- Construction of 3rd and 4th FD modules
- ✓ (over)constrain oscillation parameters with unprecedented precision
- ✓ expand the reach of DUNE in low-energy neutrino physics and BSM searches

➤ Module of Opportunity (FD4)

Opportunity to implement **innovative technologies** improving the physics reach of DUNE

The SoLAR Project

Goal:

Expand the physics reach of DUNE with a **multipurpose LArTPC** improving the performance at low-energy.

Readout system innovation:

Pixel readout plane will enhance event reconstruction, while replacing TPC wires is expected to simplify construction and installation

Arapuca-style modules + **VUV SiPMs** integrated on the anode
Exploit the light signal in LAr to perform

- Enhance effective **light yield**
- Improved **light uniformity**
- **combined Q + L calorimetry**: Target $\Delta E/E \approx 7\%$

University & INFN
Milano-Bicocca

University of
Bern

Imperial, Manchester, Edinburgh,
Sheffield, Queen Mary

LBL, UC Berkeley
MIT

CIEMAT

The SoLAR V1 Prototype (2022)

Detector specs

➤ Charge readout:

256, $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ pads, readout by 4 LArPix v2a ASIC + PACMAN

➤ Light readout:

16 Hamamatsu S13370-6050CN ($6 \times 6 \text{ mm}^2$) + Cold pre-amp + Warm amp + 62.5 MS/s digitizer

➤ Anode assembly:

Three stacked PCB layers to accommodate SiPMs packaging
SiPM floating bias to enhance charge collection

Test outcome

- combined operation of charge+light sensors
- calorimetric response ok

SoLAR Coll., JINST 19 (2024) 11

The SoLAR V2 Prototype (2023)

Motivations:

- More pixels and more SiPMs
- Better assessment of readout performance
- First test of combined charge+light analysis

Run plan:

- LED calibration run
- Cosmic-ray run
- ^{60}Co source run

Results:

🔊 Preprint out 📄 [arXiv:2512.10830](https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.10830)

The SoLAR V2 Prototype

- Tile dimension: $32 \times 32 \text{ cm}^2$
(active area $25.6 \times 25.6 \text{ cm}^2$)
- Divided into 8×8 regions (64 — 4 pixel, 1 SiPM)
- 20 LArPix v2b (room for 64)
- 64 Hamamatsu VUV4 SiPM
- Complete re-design of the PCB

SoLAR tile V1

SoLAR tile V2

Single multilayer PCB

Three PCB stacked

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Single multilayer PCB

Operated in a $33 \times 33 \times 30 \text{ cm}^3$ LArTPC

DAQ System

> Charge readout system:

LArPix ASICs read out via a **single** cable to a **PACMAN** unit outside the cryostat

> Light readout system:

Cold pre-amplifiers + warm amplifiers + 14-bit 62.5 MS/s digitizer boards

> Light readout system gives a trigger marker to PACMAN when signal goes above threshold (2 p.e.)

Calibration

Charge readout system:

- Forced triggers on all channels of each single ASIC to measure relative pedestal offsets
- Issues with one inactive ASIC limited the readout of the full tile (reconfiguring the readout network still possible)
- Trigger threshold set at $\approx 3.8 \text{ ke}^-$

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Light readout system:

- Anode flashed with a LED
- Study the SiPM response at different bias (44–46 V) and gain settings (12, 24 dB)
- Channel-wise response model for pulse deconvolution

Cosmic-ray run

Event 81 - Charge = $6.74\text{E}+05$ e - Light = $5.60\text{E}+01$ p.e.

≈ 80 min of cosmic-ray data
(≈ 50 k tracks)

- Test integration of charge and light readout systems on the same PCB
- Verify charge readout system reconstruction performance
- Test the potential of granular light readout

SiPM system performance

- Charge on single SiPMs goes from few to $\mathcal{O}(10^2)$ p.e.
- Total charge on all SiPMs for reconstructed tracks (length > 4 cm) goes from $\mathcal{O}(50)$ to $\mathcal{O}(10^3)$ p.e.

- Average μ pulse shape fitted with a double-exponential model
- Short $\tau_t = (789 \pm 13)$ ns indicates contamination
- Light yield correction factor $f_{\text{purity}} = 0.61$

Charge readout system performance - track reconstruction

Track reconstruction:

- Reconstruction of cosmic- μ tracks must deal with inactive areas (SiPMs, inactive ASICs, bad channels)
- Custom track reconstruction algorithm based on DBSCAN clustering + RANSAC regression
- Track length distribution features due to inactive areas

Energy deposition measurement:

- Electron lifetime 1.87(18) ms
- COMSOL-based estimate a 6% loss of collected charge due to field distortions around the SiPMs
- Measured dQ/dx distribution consistent with ND-LAr results 5.30 ke $^{-}$ /mm most probable value [DUNE, Instruments 8 (2024) 3, 41]

Combined charge+light energy reconstruction

- ▶ Sample of through-going μ (single track, len > 4 cm, score > 0.5)
- ▶ Spatial effects on light collection estimated integrating a MC-based light-map over the reconstructed track

- ▶ Given the **track topology** reconstructed with the charge readout, one can estimate the **expected light** collected by each SiPM
- ▶ Good agreement with the data in the relative SiPM signal intensities

Combined charge+light energy reconstruction

Slope of L_{exp} vs L_{data} indicates that the model describes scintillation light propagation and detection with good accuracy.

Use the model to extract scintillation light emission per unit length

$$\frac{dL}{dx} = \left. \frac{dE}{dx} \right|_{\text{mip}} \cdot (\text{LY} \cdot f_{\text{purity}}) = \frac{L_{\text{data}}}{\ell_{\text{TPC track}} \cdot \text{PDE} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{SiPM}}} \bar{\Omega}_i}$$

Cosmic- μ are not the ideal sample for Q+L calorimetry studies
 Dedicated run with a ^{60}Co source was collected during the same test and the analysis is ongoing

Next steps: SoLAr towards ProtoDUNE Run III

- **Large scale** engineering **prototype** for mass production, installation, and integration of Phase II components at full Far Detector dimensions
- Proposal for a **Optical and Charge Hybrid Run** at NP02 submitted to the CERN SPSC
- Proposed operation in **2028–2029** during SPS LS3

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(SoLAR and Pixels) Goals:

- Test pixel charge readout with m-scale drift
- Assess the optical gain from the SoLAR SiPMs vs depth
- Validate integration for large anode planes

SoLAR R&D:

- Redesign of the SoLAR tile PCB for easier integration into a pixelated anode plane
- Test new readout options for SiPMs (LightPix)

Conclusions and outlooks

- Analysis of **SoLAR V2 cosmic-ray run** has been finalized [arXiv:2512.10830](https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.10830)
- Demonstration of **combined operation of charge and light readout systems** on the same PCB, with performance in line with expectations
- First steps towards a **combined Q+L energy reconstruction**, more detailed studies with a dedicated ^{60}Co run are ongoing
- **Next steps:** deploying SoLAR tiles in **ProtoDUNE Run III**
 - PCB redesign to ease integration with pixelated anode planes
 - Planning LightPix SiPM readout tests

Backup material

SiPM waveform processing

Inversion + Baseline subtraction

Deconvolution

Hit finding

SoLAR V2 run: 2023-07-06 19:16:44
event: 12930 - ts [ns]: 629760
SiPM board 215537201 - ch 38

Combined charge+light energy reconstruction

- Select a “golden sample” of through-going muons (single track, length > 5 cm, score > 0.5)
- Extrapolate the track inside the TPC volume (\mathbf{x}_{in} , \mathbf{x}_{out} , \hat{u}_{track})
- Compute the expected light signal on the SiPM i as

$$q_i = \sum_{k=1}^N \left. \frac{dE}{dx} \right|_{mip} \cdot \delta x \cdot (LY(\mathcal{E}) \cdot f_{purity}) \cdot PDE \cdot \Omega_i(\mathbf{x}_{in} + k \delta x \hat{u}_{track})$$

with $\Omega_i(\mathbf{x})$ the **visibility** of SiPM i from point \mathbf{x} (obtained from interpolating a MC-based visibility map)

- The total expected light signal is then

$$L_{exp} = \left. \frac{dE}{dx} \right|_{mip} \cdot \ell_{track}^{TPC} \cdot (LY(\mathcal{E}) \cdot f_{purity}) \cdot PDE \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_{SiPM}} \bar{\Omega}_i(\mathbf{x}_{in}, \hat{u}_{track})$$

SiPM layout

